

2nd International Conference on Big Data and Applications (BDAP 2021)

April 24~25, 2021, Copenhagen, Denmark

<https://csit2021.org/bdap/index.html>

Scope

2nd International Conference on Big Data and Applications (BDAP 2021) will act as a major forum for the presentation of innovative ideas, approaches, developments, and research projects in the areas of Big Data. It will also serve to facilitate the exchange of information between researchers and industry professionals to discuss the latest issues and advancement in the area of Big Data.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in Big Data.

Topics:

- Big Data Techniques, Models and Algorithms
- Big Data Infrastructure and Platform
- Big Data Search and Mining
- Bioinformatics Big Data Security, Privacy and Trust
- Big Data Applications, Multimedia etc
- Big Data Tools and Systems
- Big Data Mining
- Big Data Management
- Cloud and Grid Computing for Big Data
- Machine Learning and AI for Big Data
- Big Data Analytics and Social Media
- 5G and Networks for Big Data
- Big Data Applications in Education, Healthcare... etc.

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **April 03, 2021 (Final Call)**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **BDAP 2021**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journals

- [International Journal of Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process \(IJKP\)](#)
- [International Journal of Database Management Systems \(IJDMS\)](#)
- [International Journal on Web Service Computing \(IJWSC\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)](#) ^{New} - ESCI(WOS) Indexed

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : April 03, 2021(Final Call)**
- Notification : April 18, 2021
- Final Manuscript Due : April 20, 2021

Contact us

Here's where you can reach us: bdap@csit2021.org or bdapconf@yahoo.com

Submission Link

<https://csit2021.org/submission/index.php>

More Details Please Visit

<https://csit2021.org/bdap/index.html>

Co-located Events

- [8th International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technology \(CSIT 2021\)](#)
- [7th International Conference on Image Processing and Pattern Recognition \(IPPR 2021\)](#)
- [7th International Conference on Software Engineering \(SOENG 2021\)](#)
- [9th International Conference of Security, Privacy and Trust Management \(SPTM 2021\)](#)
- [10th International conference on Parallel, Distributed Computing and Applications \(IPDCA 2021\)](#)
- [7th International Conference on Data Mining \(DaMi 2021\)](#)
- [7th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Soft Computing \(AIS 2021\)](#)
- [2nd International Conference on Natural Language Processing & Applications \(NLPA 2021\)](#)
- [2nd International Conference on Advanced Machine Learning \(AMLA 2021\)](#)